

A review of Vocational Education and Training in North Macedonia

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Final version

Markus Maurer

Professor of Vocational Education, Zurich University of Teacher Education

Ognen Spasovski

Professor of Psychology, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje

Corresponding address:

Prof. Dr. Markus Maurer
Pädagogische Hochschule Zürich
Abteilung Sekundarstufe II/Berufsbildung
Lagerstrasse 5 (LAD 214)
CH-8090 Zürich
+41 43 305 66 12
markus.maurer@phzh.ch

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Executive summary

This report examines formal and non-formal vocational education (VET) in North Macedonia, a policy area that has gained significant importance in recent years and has received support from numerous international partners.

The report acknowledges that important reforms have been initiated in formal VET in recent years with the aim of enhancing its relevance to the job market. The primary focus has been on promoting dual VET and increasing the share of VET at the secondary level. While the report notes significant progress in both areas, it highlights the limited prevalence of productive work within dual VET, casting uncertainty on sustained business support. Such efforts also face the challenge that young people primarily engage in formal VET to access higher education, largely due to the fact that formal VET qualifications have little significance in the job market. Against this backdrop, the report suggests a re-evaluation of the significance and role of secondary VET from a policy perspective. A more practical orientation of VET would require tighter restrictions on access to higher education. Such a restriction is indeed politically sensitive. However, if the key stakeholders are not willing to consider it, a more practical orientation for secondary VET will practically be unfeasible, except in a few VET sectors where job market access requires a corresponding vocational qualification (e.g., in the health sector).

The report also indicates that non-formal adult VET is heavily utilised, albeit less within state-sponsored programmes and more in the free market. Overall, it appears that primarily the official recognised offers, i.e., those verified by the Adult Education Centre, are underutilised, mainly because these non-formal qualifications hold even less weight in the job market than the formal qualifications. Simplifying the verification process for all involved parties and systematically involving labour market representatives in the development of standards would be crucial improvements to address these challenges.

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1 Introduction

Improving the development of vocational skills has become an important political priority in North Macedonia, in view of their potential to improve young people's access to the labour market, but also to increase the country's economic performance. Against this background, policy makers, business representatives together with civil society and the international community are committed to reforms in this field of policy. Much has been achieved in recent years: enrolments in formal vocational education and training (VET) at the upper secondary level are increasing overall (State Statistical Office, 2022c), growing numbers of companies are involved in training activities and non-formal vocational qualifications have also gained in importance. In addition, the comparability of VET in North Macedonia with that of other European countries has greatly increased thanks to the Macedonian Qualifications Framework (MQF) (Ministry of Education and Science, 2016). However, great challenges persist: companies in particular often complain that VET is still not sufficiently geared to the requirements of the labour market and that the practical and social skills of many VET graduates remain deficient. Against this background, our report reviews the country's VSD system to assess the current status as well as to identify gaps and areas of improvement.

The review focuses in particular on two parts of this system, on the formal VET system on the one hand and on non-formal VET, i.e., non-formal forms of vocational skills development on the other. The formal VET system includes the programmes regulated by the VET Law. These include the two-, three- and four-year programmes at the upper secondary level, as well as the post-secondary programmes that lead to a recognised vocational qualification. Non-formal VET programmes are those that impart vocational skills but do not lead to vocational qualifications recognised in the education system. Such programmes include vocational courses for unemployed adults as well as commercial training in a number of vocational fields, such as IT. As they are of some importance for the preparation for upper secondary programmes, vocational counselling services are also addressed in this report. Yet, the review does not focus on vocationally oriented programmes at the tertiary level.

Reviewing the VET system in North Macedonia as a whole and not focussing on a specific project or reform, this report is based on three types of data. Firstly, official statistical data related to the programmes and offerings presented here, as well as data concerning the economy and labour market. Secondly, text documents, particularly legal texts, curricula, and other official documents (e.g., policies). Thirdly, qualitative interviews with representatives from relevant authorities, associations, schools, and individual VET students. These interviews were conducted between late September and mid-November. Some of the findings are also informed by our previous research, which has explored the validation of prior learning and policy transfer in Macedonian VSD (Maurer & Spasovski, 2022, 2023).

2 Context of VET in North-Macedonia: Developments and policy developments

The following section examines developments in four areas that have a particularly strong influence on VET policy in North Macedonia. These are the areas of demography, the development of the economy and the labour market, the dynamics of the entire education system (also beyond VET) and relations with the European Union, which North Macedonia would like to join as soon as possible.

2.1 Demography

One of the biggest challenges facing the country is its shrinking and aging population. The number of people residing in North Macedonia decreased from 2,022.547 to 1,836.713 between 2002 and 2021, representing a decline of approximately 10 percent (State Statistical Office, 2003, 2022a). The reasons for this decline can be attributed, on the one hand, to decreasing birth rates and, on the other hand, to significant emigration to Western European countries and the USA, Australia and Canada. Due to low birth rates and the fact that predominantly younger individuals are emigrating, the average age of the population has increased in recent years, rising from 37,5 (38,3 for women and 36,7 for men) in 2011 to 40,8 (41,7 for women and 39,9 for men) in 2021 (State Statistical Office, 2003, 2022a). This demographic shift has had an impact on various aspects of life and policy areas, particularly on the labour market and education, as well as the country's taxation and pension policies.

2.2 Economy and Labour Market

In comparison to other countries in the region, North Macedonia's economy has experienced relatively limited growth since its transition to independence. The collapse of Yugoslavia initially led to a decline in industry, particularly in urban areas, and a significant increase in the informal economy, where substantial portions of the population continue to find income. Over time, attempts were made to attract investors from Western Europe, primarily with the help of the comparatively low wage levels. However, many of these manufacturing industries now face a pronounced shortage of skilled workers, which some larger companies have addressed by importing labour, often from Asian countries such as Nepal or Pakistan. This shortage of skilled workers poses a significant challenge for numerous other sectors characterised by relatively low wages and lower social status, such as construction and gastronomy, and is exacerbated by demographic challenges. In contrast, the shortage of skilled workers is relatively less pronounced in the proportionally small but well-paid and socially respected service sector in larger cities.

Simultaneously, the country is faced with a very high rate of youth unemployment. Whilst the total unemployment rate was 14.4% in 2022, it was 32.5% for the population on age 15-24, especially among individuals with a university degree (and relatively less so among those with a VET qualification from a middle school) (State Statistical Office, 2023b). The paradoxical situation of a severe shortage of skilled workers alongside extremely high unemployment in the country is typically explained by the fact that being a registered unemployed person is ultimately more attractive than taking a low-paying job, especially since many registered unemployed individuals earn income in the informal economy and benefit from certain social services (e.g., healthcare) not available to the unregistered unemployed.

2.3 Relations with the European Union and with other international partners

Many of the current reforms in North Macedonia can be viewed within the context of the country's European integration process, which continues to be marked by numerous uncertainties and challenges. North Macedonia has been an EU candidate country since 2005. For many years, the name dispute with Greece was the central reason for the slow progress in the accession negotiations, and since the name change, the process has been delayed further (Koneska, 2019). As a candidate country, North Macedonia is financially supported by the IPA. In the first two phases

(2007-2013 and 2014-2020), more than 1.28 billion EUR were budgeted for this purpose (European Commission, 2017; Mojsavska, 2016). However, the EU's financial and technical support goes back much further: it began in the 1990s, first in the framework of humanitarian aid, and was then continued in the framework of EU development aid for countries in the Balkans (Phare and CARDS programmes) (Radosavljevik-Bojceva & Temelkov, 2011). At the same time, North Macedonia is still supported directly by individual EU member states (such as Germany) within the framework of bilateral cooperation, and by countries outside the EU (such as Switzerland) (Mitevski, 2016).

In the face of high youth unemployment in countries around the world, VET has become a central theme of international development cooperation. This trend is evident in North Macedonia, too: all major bilateral and multilateral official development partners deal with this topic in one way or another. VET – and in connection with it also adult education – have become central issues in North Macedonian education policy.

First of all, cooperation with the European Union is of particular importance, especially because North Macedonia has been in negotiations to enter the union since 2005. Although the member states of the EU enjoy a comparatively high degree of autonomy in education policy (Garben, 2012; Lancos, 2018), they, and with them the candidate countries, are very much oriented towards the EU's education strategies. The EU supports such harmonisation efforts in North Macedonia through the Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance, which is currently (2021-2027) in its third phase (European Commission, 2021, 2022).

A donor with considerable visibility in VET policy is the Swiss Development and Cooperation Agency (SDC). One of its projects has a specific focus on the promotion of dual VET, whereby the project strives to make experiences from Switzerland accessible to policy makers and implementers from North Macedonia (Helvetas Macedonia, Macedonian Civic Education Centre, & Economic Chamber of Macedonia, 2017). Another major donor is the World Bank, which has supported VET in North Macedonia through various loans. For several years, it had a strong focus on curriculum development in VET programmes, which were to become more competency-based and more oriented towards the needs of the labour market (World Bank, 2013).

2.4 Education

The recent reforms in North Macedonia's VET system need to be seen in the context of the overall development of the education system. The following outlines a few particularly important aspects of this system and its development.

2.4.1 Education system

The formal education system in North Macedonia essentially comprises three levels:

Table 1: Synthesis of the Macedonian formal education system

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Elementary Education (9 years): This level corresponds to both primary and lower-secondary education from an international perspective. It encompasses the first nine years of compulsory education. 2. Compulsory Secondary Education (the current Law on SE doesn't define what level is compulsory. The new draft Law on Secondary Education defines it at NQF level 2). At secondary level, there are two tracks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gymnasium Track: It includes a 4-year Gymnasium programme culminating in the completion of the state matriculation examination ("<i>state matura</i>"). This track prepares students for higher education and provides a more general academic curriculum. - Vocational Track: This track offers programmes that typically span 2 to 4 years, focusing on vocational and technical skills development, while also offering opportunities for educational mobility. Once the draft law on VET comes into force, formal VET will finish either with VET matura or VET exam. 3. Post-Secondary and Higher Education: This level includes institutions such as universities, colleges, and other higher education institutions. It caters to students seeking tertiary education and specialised training beyond secondary school.

2.4.2 Enrolment rates and dropout

Since Yugoslavian times, enrolment rates have been growing at all levels of the education system, to which both compulsory secondary education and an education policy aimed at social inclusion certainly have contributed (OECD, 2019).

The growth of enrolment at secondary level was particularly significant. However, our calculations reveal three major challenges at this level.

- About 10% of all young people do not start secondary education, despite it being compulsory.¹ Data suggest that there is a dropout indication between primary and secondary education.²
- Many young people drop out of their secondary education, often resulting from economic factors like employment in the informal sector, family obligations or early marriages. Thus, according to our own calculations based on official statistical data, only 68% of those aged between 15 and 19 were attending school during the academic year 2021/22.³ This figure needs some caution in interpretation as some students may not attend the full four-year secondary education. Nevertheless, it is likely that the proportion of people between 25-34 years old with a secondary school completion is lower than the 82% suggested by the OECD (2019).
- The total number of students in secondary education has been dropping over the last years, decreasing from 71,811 in the academic year 2020/21 to 65,733 in 2023/24 (Ministry of Education and Science, 2023d; State Statistical Office, 2022c).

Additionally, there has been a significant surge in higher education enrolment, a trend strongly supported by the establishment of new universities, many of which are private (OECD, 2019).

2.4.3 The challenge of education quality

Despite the increasing enrolment numbers, low-quality education remains a persistent problem. The country's PISA results are very low compared to other countries in the region. Similarly, the quality of higher education is also regarded as low (Shasivari, 2018; Spasovski & Pecakovska, 2020): This is primarily attributed to the lenient admissions practices, especially the fact that the number of university places exceeds the number of graduates with a state matura (graduating either from the gymnasium or from a 4 year VET programme) (State Statistical Office, 2022b).

¹ Precise and regular statistics regarding dropouts from schools and the state statistical office are unavailable. However, a comparison between census data and school enrolment data allows for certain conclusions to be drawn. According to data from the State Statistical Office, the 2021 Census revealed a population of 20,212 individuals aged 15, the typical age for enrolment in the first year of secondary school. However, only 18,110 students were enrolled in the first year of secondary school during the academic year 2021/22, constituting 90% of the age group (State Statistical Office, 2022c).

² At the end of the academic year 2021/22, 19,102 students completed ninth grade primary education. However, at the beginning of the next academic year, only 17,978 students enrolled in the first year of secondary education, approximately six percent fewer than those completing primary education (State Statistical Office, 2022c).

³ As an estimate, data from the 2021 Census indicates a population aged between 15 and 19 at 104,035, while the total number of students across all four years of secondary education, typically within that age range, for the academic year 2021/22, stands at 71,018 (State Statistical Office, 2022a, 2022c), which suggests an net secondary enrolment rate of 68% of the age group.

3 Formal Vocational Education and Training

This section of the report addresses the offerings regulated by the VET Law. These include the two-year, three-year, and four-year programmes at the upper secondary level. Additionally, it covers post-secondary offerings that lead to a recognised vocational qualification.

3.1 Formal VET in North Macedonia in a nutshell

In international comparison, secondary VET in North Macedonia holds significant importance, with more than 64% percent of students attending VET schools offering such programmes, while 35% attend gymnasiums, and 1-2% attend art and sport secondary programmes in the end of the 2022/23 and 2023/24 academic year. This share of vocational education has even increased in recent years (reaching from 60 percent in the year 2020/21 to 64.1 percent in 2023/24) (Ministry of Education and Science, 2023d; State Statistical Office, 2022c). Growth can be attributed primarily to policies that have imposed stricter access to the academic programmes of gymnasiums. These measures were accompanied by comprehensive public awareness programmes aimed at persuading the public of the value of vocational education. These efforts likely contributed to the increasing share of vocational education at the secondary level.

Overall, policy makers are of the view that VET has become more popular among learners and their parents, although the data only suggests that the relative proportion of VET at secondary level has increased. It's important to note that this shift may have various underlying causes.

3.1.1 VET programmes and enrolment

Within vocational education, the four-year programmes are particularly well-attended, with approximately 91 percent of all secondary VET students enrolled in this programme in 2022/23. The enrolment in two-year programmes has become completely insignificant, and only 9 percent of VET students are joining the three-year programmes, but many of them are continuing with one more year, finally graduating from the four-year programme (Ministry of Education and Science, 2023d; State Statistical Office, 2022c). Even when considering the selected VET sectors, there are significant differences (see Table 2).

Table 2: VET sectors by student numbers in 2022/23 (Ministry of Education and Science, 2023c)

VET sector	Number of students	VET sector	Number of students
Economy, law and trade	3499	Agriculture-veterinary	872
Health	3324	Personal services	810
Electro-technical	3037	Traffic engineering	873
Machine engineering	2339	Textile and leather products	738
Chemical-technology	1103	Forestry	293
Hospitality, hoteliers	1014	Geology, mining and metallurgy	277
Construction-geodesy	914	Graphic and printing	118

In addition to these secondary VET programmes, post-secondary programmes are also part of formal VET. Yet, the number of post-secondary education graduates remains insignificant. Most programmes have virtually no students – one of the only exceptions being the one for "driving instructors" (i.e., 184 out of 258 students at this level in 2017/2018) (Ministry of Education and Science, 2023a; State Statistical Office, 2023a).

3.1.2 Governance and financing

Formal VET is regulated primarily by two laws: the Law on Secondary Education, which defines aspects such as the duration of programmes at this educational level, qualifications, and associated enrolment criteria (Republic of Macedonia, 2013a), and the Law on Vocational Education (Republic of Macedonia, 2006), which regulates further details of VET programmes, including the duration of practical training (“*практична настава*”). Additionally, there is the Law on the Qualifications Framework (Republic of Macedonia, 2013b), which assigns all educational programmes in the country to a specific level within this framework. These three laws have new drafts prepared in recent years but have not yet been passed by Parliament. Based on this legal framework, the Teaching Plans, which specify the weekly number of lessons in each subject for each program, are developed.

Two central authorities are particularly crucial for the governance and management of VET in the country. Firstly, the Ministry of Education is responsible for developing the legal framework and overseeing its implementation. Despite the decentralization of education, where municipalities typically own individual VET schools, these schools must obtain approval from the Ministry for their offerings, as municipalities receive funding for operating the schools based on student enrolment.

The second important authority is the VET Centre, primarily responsible for developing the curricular basis for all VET programmes. This includes occupational and qualifications standards and the training programmes based on these standards for the vocational aspects of VET programmes. On the other hand, the Bureau for Development of Education is responsible for developing the content of general-education subjects. Ultimately, the VET Centre is also responsible for quality assurance in VET. Despite the critical role of the VET Centre in the functioning of vocational education in North Macedonia, this authority has very limited personnel, making it challenging to carry out its tasks effectively.

3.1.3 Vocational qualifications in the labour market

A fundamental fact that is insufficiently reflected in the VET policy debates in North Macedonia, in our opinion, significantly hinders the effective implementation of many VET reforms: vocational qualifications have limited significance in the current job market. Most jobs in the formal labour market do not require formal vocational qualifications at all (Maurer & Spasovski, 2022). This applies to the vast majority of jobs, such as those in agriculture, manufacturing, construction, or gastronomy. Depending on the industry and region, not even completed elementary education is expected in some cases, even though graduates of secondary or higher education can also be found in many of these industries. In contrast, there are occupations in more regulated sectors where an appropriate vocational qualification is generally expected, such as for caregivers in healthcare. Such regulations were much more common during the time of Yugoslavia than they are today. For example, working as an electrician often required completing a three-year VET program, and certain tasks could only be performed by individuals with post-secondary qualifications. In particular *owners* of businesses, like hairdressing salons, were required to have such post-secondary qualifications during the Yugoslav era. Even though this regulation still exists, there is, for workshops that have already been opened, there are rare checks to verify if these individuals (or the other employed) still hold the required qualification to participate, lowering the demand for such post-secondary qualifications.

The high shortage of skilled workers also contributes to employers in many industries not requiring vocational (or other) qualifications. In the mentioned, relatively well-paid and socially respected service sector in larger cities, most employees have at least a bachelor's degree. This includes the numerous jobs in public administration, as well as jobs in some highly profitable sectors of the private sector or in non-governmental Organisations.

Against this backdrop, it can be observed that from the perspective of many young people, there are few incentives to obtain a vocational qualification unless it simultaneously provides access to higher education or access to a relatively well-paying job with further career opportunities, such as in large corporations.

3.2 Reform agenda of the last 10 years and support by international partners

Given the high youth unemployment and the high demand for skilled workers, the country's policy makers, with the support of representatives of the world of work in North Macedonia and the international community, are making efforts to strengthen VET. This commitment became evident, particularly in the VET Strategy of 2013, the development, and implementation of which was initially supported by the European Union (under the IPA framework) and the World Bank (Ministry of Education and Science, 2013a). Clearly, these reform efforts are aimed at aligning VET in the country with EU standards.

The strengthening of VET is intended to be achieved, in particular, through better alignment with the labour market. In this context, as part of the World Bank project mentioned above, four-year VET programmes were reformed through curriculum modularization and the enhancement of work-based learning. At the same time, the National Qualifications Framework was established, and a large number of occupational and qualifications standards have been defined, which have been classified within this framework. Also of significance is the attempt to specifically strengthen selected VET schools through the creation of regional VET centres, primarily supported by the EU under the third IPA phase, and the EU-supported project "EU for Youth" (European Union, 2023a, 2023b). Particular attention has also been given to efforts to introduce a dual VET model, especially within the framework of the project E4E (Education for Employment), supported by the Swiss government (SDC, 2023). These reforms will now be examined in more detail in the following.

3.3 Development and implementation of "dual VET"

3.3.1 Overview of reform activities in the past years

The introduction of dual VET in North Macedonia is part of long-standing efforts to increase the importance of practical learning in VET. This reform idea became clearly visible in 2010, when some strategy papers for VET prepared with the help of the EU suggested that VET students should dedicate a minimum of 40 percent of their time to practical learning, with one third of it being training at company-level (Ministry of Education and Science, 2010a, 2010b, 2010c).

Essentially, the aim is to conduct the practical components, which are present in all two, three, and four-year programmes, as extensively as possible within business settings. In the traditional training model, this practical training was carried out within the schools themselves, complemented by company-based internships in the summer holidays ("summer/ferial practice"). Efforts to involve businesses in education became particularly visible since 2012 when the concept of "work-based learning" was introduced (ETF, 2020). The idea was to allow VET learners to undertake their practical training in multiple companies, that entered into Memoranda of Understandings with VET schools.

In recent years, the concept of the "dual model" has been developed, where VET students are supposed to undergo their practical training primarily in *one* company throughout their entire education. There were activities in various areas, especially in the context of the mentioned E4E project funded by SDC (SDC, 2023)

- *Curriculum development:* Since 2019/20, reformed VET programmes developed by the VET Centre have been operational. Over the past year, with support from the E4E project, work-based learning programmes have been initiated for all programmes (sectors, qualifications) where dual education is implemented, aligning with those developed by the VET Centre. Study programmes

for the second year were developed in 2022. Currently, study programmes for the third year are in development, with plans to prepare for the fourth one next year.

- *Didactic materials*: There is a chronic shortage of such materials, especially textbooks, across all sectors, leading teachers to frequently rely on internet resources. As part of the E4E project, an initiative has been launched to aid in the creation of didactic materials tailored to meet the needs of teachers.
- *Teacher training*: Given the necessity for teachers to stay abreast of technological advancements and effectively implement dual VET, 47 professional staff members from schools underwent training during the initial phase of the E4E project, followed by an additional 200 in the second phase.
- *Mentorship programmes*: During the first phase of the project, 47 mentors within companies underwent training to enhance their competencies in implementing dual VET, followed by 200 mentors in the second phase.
- *Incentives for companies and learners*: The E4E project does not provide financial incentives. The matter of companies benefitting from participation in dual VET remains unresolved, with policy-makers yet to initiate specific discussions, while the proposed new VET law does not address this issue. Regarding learners, all students enrolled in dual VET currently receive a monthly fee of MKD 3500 (approximately 53 Euros). The proposed new VET law anticipates a contract linking this monthly fee to a percentage of the official average salary in the country.
- *Occupational and Qualification Standards*: The VET Centre developed new standards for 360 occupations and 110 qualifications, all structured around learning outcomes and customised to meet the demands of the labour market. These standards were subsequently approved by the Ministry of Education and Science (MOES). Additionally, the VET Centre reformed the VET study programmes, configuring them in a modular format. This entails the programmes being composed of modules that form complete units, transferrable across various but interconnected study programmes.

3.3.2 Statistical information

The percentage of students engaged in dual VET has notably increased in recent years. The share of VET classes conducted in a practical working environment rose from 60% in the school years 2020/21 to 64% in the school years 2022/23 and 2023/24. In the academic year 2023/24, there are 42,153 students enrolled in VET, distributed across 2,151 classes, accounting for 64.1% of all students in secondary education. Among these, 14,273 are participants in dual VET spread over 590 classes, making up 34% of all students in VET—a substantial increase from the 10,961 enrolled in 2020/21. In the current first year of VET, there are 11,513 students enrolled, representing 69% of all students enrolled in the first year of secondary education (Ministry of Education and Science, several years).

The increase in the number of students, classes, schools, and companies engaged in dual VET from 2020-21 to 2022/23 is detailed in Table 4 below.

Table 3: Students, classes, schools and companies in dual VET

Academic year	Students	Classes	Schools	Companies
2020/21	98	11	8	16
2021/22	1486	97	46	210
2022/23	2763	225	61	450

Table 4 below illustrates that the approximate proportion of dual VET students varies depending on the VET sector. This percentage is particularly high in sectors such as "forestry," "personal services," or "textile," whereas it is much lower in the "traffic engineering" sector. In our perspective, these differences are not the outcome of deliberate policy decisions (e.g., concerning the economic

relevance of individual sectors) and are not result of a well-thought decisions toward sustainable outcomes.

Table 4: Dual VET programmes by sectors (Ministry of Education and Science, 2023d)

VET Sector	Number of VET students in 2022/23	Number of dual VET students in 2023/24	Share of dual VET students
Forestry	293	112	38
Personal services	810	223	28
Textile and leather products	738	178	24
Agriculture-veterinary	872	200	23
Economy, law and trade	3499	775	22
Chemical-technology	1103	238	22
Health	3324	706	21
Machine engineering	2339	490	21
Hospitality, hoteliers	1014	212	21
Electro-technical	3037	570	19
Construction-geodesy	914	115	13
Graphic and printing	118	14	12
Geology, mining and metallurgy	277	18	6
Traffic engineering	873	44	5

The surge in VET in general and in dual VET in particular was supported by two primary measures undertaken by the government and the MOES to reduce enrolment in gymnasiums and promote the attractiveness and participation in VET. Firstly, an extensive campaign aimed to boost the involvement of companies willing to host trainees. The count of schools and companies engaged in VET programmes offering an 'increased number of practice classes' raised significantly in 2020/21 and 2022/23, despite the challenges posed by the pandemic: from 8 VET schools (out of 75), and from 16 companies involved to 450. Secondly, authorities facilitated training sessions for employees to become in-company trainers. Approximately 1000 employees participated in such training initiatives conducted by the VET Centre within the framework of the E4E project.

3.3.3 Assessment of progress in dual VET so far

Strengths: Stakeholders widely appreciate the dual VET model in North Macedonia, recognizing its effectiveness in imparting practical skills to learners. Positive strides have been made in the VET system, especially evident in internships where students actively apply theoretical knowledge within professional settings. Participating companies generally report satisfaction with students' performance, indicating a promising aspect of this approach.

Challenges and Concerns: Despite its potential, dual VET faces several challenges in North Macedonia. Ensuring mutual benefit for all involved parties—schools, businesses, and students—is crucial for sustained participation. The considerable effort demanded from both educational institutions and companies poses a long-term sustainability question, particularly regarding perceived benefits. Schools and teachers seek greater support from companies, but also express concerns about regulatory compliance. Additionally, the motivation of students, currently bolstered by financial incentives, may not be sustained without such incentives. Companies engage in training without immediate economic gains, expecting policy changes for future profitability. Moreover, disparities in student involvement in productive activities within companies and insufficient practical equipment in VET schools pose risks to the effectiveness of the program. Lastly, a mismatch exists between students' university aspirations and companies' preference for learners that want to enter the world of work, creating a significant challenge.

3.4 Further reforms in VET: Ambitions and outcomes

3.4.1 Improving remedial VET

Access to Remedial Programmes: In North Macedonia, secondary education legislation allows for enrolment in part-time education for individuals who have completed primary education. Additionally, the law permits entry into two-year VET programmes for those without completed primary education, with the condition to complete it concurrently with the VET program. This legislation extends the scope of VET programmes to include 2- and 3-year courses conducted in adult education institutions. Part-time students, enrolled in remedial education programmes, engage in self-learning and undertake exams based on specific curricula. Eligibility criteria encompass various conditions such as age, illness, employment status, school expulsion, and other conditions regulated by individual school statutes. Statistics from the 2016/17 academic year reflect notably low participation rates in part-time education, underscoring the limited utilization of this educational measure. To improve the situation, the MOES realised a project to support adults to finish part-time VET, mostly 4-year programmes, and mostly in the sectors of economy, electro and machine engineering, chemical-technology, agriculture, food processing, textile and traffic engineering. 918 adults finish it in 2018, 1252 in 2019, 621 in 2020, 1453 in 2021, and 832 in 2022.

"Second Chance" Programmes: Introduced through the new Law on AE, "Second Chance" programmes offer an opportunity to complete specific levels of formal VET through part-time education. As a pilot initiative, these programmes were launched in 2022, aiming to assist NEETs (individuals Not in Education, Employment, or Training). The pilot programmes were funded by both the state budget and international donors. These initiatives specifically targeted vulnerable groups, striving to facilitate the completion of one year of formal VET within a single semester. A recent initiative by the Employment Service Agency, in collaboration with multiple educational bodies, aimed to support 130 NEETs from vulnerable groups. Following a call for applicants under 29 years old in December, 84 individuals received financial support to pursue a certain level of VET in public VET schools. The completion data for this initiative is currently being processed, and plans for a subsequent call to fill the remaining 46 places are imminent.

Limitations of Remedial Education: The shortcomings of part-time education primarily stem from its heavy reliance on self-education, often resulting in minimal learning support and infrequent exposure to work-based learning opportunities. Furthermore, the fixed timeframes for grade completion pose limitations, as all students, regardless of their level of competency, are required to spend the same period for completing the program. Consequently, this structure may hinder the effective improvement of vocational competencies among students engaged in remedial education.

Alignment of Remedial Education with VNFIL: Efforts to align remedial education with the Validation of Non-Formal and Informal Learning (VNFIL) are evident through the VET Centre's implementation of "Programmes for vertical mobility". These programmes enable candidates who have completed a three-year occupation program to transition into a four-year technician program. The assessment process within these programmes resembles the validation of prior learning. However, concerns among stakeholders linger regarding the mechanisms for quality assurance in the validation process. Additionally, misconceptions persist regarding the nature of prior learning validation, fuelling apprehensions about the potential for certification without meeting defined standards. Clarifications and enhancements in didactic approaches, materials, and procedures for remedial VET, especially concerning work-based learning in companies, are areas requiring further development and attention.

3.4.2 Regional VET Centres

Establishment of Regional VET Centres (RVETCs): In 2021, the MOES undertook amendments to the existing VET law, leading to the selection of three VET schools across diverse regions – in Ohrid, Tetovo, and Kumanovo, to be designated as Regional VET Centres under the jurisdiction of the MOES. These centres were envisioned to encompass distinct sectors or departments, each responsible for a spectrum of services and developmental aspects: formal VET; adult education and Validation of Non-Formal and Informal Learning (VNFIL); research, development, and innovation; collaboration with the business sector; as well as networking, international cooperation, and marketing. However, certain departments within these centres remain non-operational, awaiting the adoption of pertinent laws necessary for their functionality.

Expansion Efforts and Project Support: Supplemented by the IPA project "Increasing attractiveness, inclusiveness, and relevance of VET and Adult Education," a comprehensive mapping and review of VET provisions were conducted across five additional regions distinct from those with established RVETCs. The aim was to identify and assist in establishing two new Regional VET Centres. Following consultations involving the MOES, VET Centre, and relevant stakeholders, governmental decisions led to the selection of the VET schools in Veles and Strumica as the two new RVETCs. Supported by the EU's "EU for Youth" project, jointly implemented by the MOES and the Ministry of Labour and Social Policy (MLSP), measures were devised to enhance youth employability by improving the quality of VET and VNFIL services offered in these centres.

Challenges and Legislative Developments: Despite these initiatives, the RVETCs currently operate below full capacity and lack the necessary equipment for high-quality vocational practice, posing a challenge in delivering top-tier VET programmes to students. The draft of the new Law on VET, undergoing Parliamentary procedures, outlines three models for establishing RVETCs: as a state/public institution, as a public-private partnership (PPP), or as an institution funded by private business initiatives (business-led centres). However, discussions persist, especially regarding the feasibility and implications of the private business initiative model, sparking ongoing debates among stakeholders. Consequently, due to pending legislative statuses, the RVETCs, for now, function quite similarly to regular VET schools.

3.4.3 Qualifications framework

The establishment of the Macedonian Qualifications Framework in 2013 is considered a significant milestone in the development of VSD in the country. The primary objectives were to enhance transparency regarding existing qualifications, increase the permeability between general education, formal VET, and non-formal adult education. Additionally, the framework was supposed to allow for the recognition of informally acquired vocational competencies in view of formal and non-formal qualifications. This initiative was also intended to strengthen the reputation of vocational education.

The framework consists of 8 levels, similar to the European Qualifications Framework. NQF makes distinction between "educational" and "vocational" qualifications. "Educational qualifications" include all diplomas awarded within the formal VET system, such as the Upper Secondary Technical Diploma at level 4 or the Craftsman Diploma at level 5. "Vocational qualifications" may be a part of the formal vocational-educational qualifications, or qualifications acquired through non-formal education, adult education or validation.

The introduction of the framework has notably led to a growing number of competency-oriented occupational and qualifications standards, which define competencies and learning outcomes for various occupations. All of these standards are associated with specific levels of the framework and ideally should be revised every 5 years to remain up-to-date. These occupational and qualifications standards serve as the curricular basis for adult education programmes and formal VET programmes at high schools. The VET Centre prepared new templates for standards for 360 occupations and 110 qualifications based on learning outcomes, tailored to the needs of the labour

market, which were further adopted by the NQF Board. In correlation with the standards, the VET Centre further revised the VET study programmes, designing them in a modular way.

The EU-funded Twinning project "Further support to the implementation of the National Qualifications Framework" (Ministry of Education and Science, 2023c), currently in progress, aims to enhance the effectiveness of the NQF by advancing and implementing quality assurance procedures, enhancing transparency, and refining the governance of skills and qualifications within the context of lifelong learning. Additionally, it strives to enhance the adaptability of education and training in accordance with labour market demands. The Twinning project supports the enhancement and upkeep of the digital qualifications register, along with the digital process for submitting and adopting an initiative for the development of an occupational standard.

The Qualifications Framework is considered well-established and recognised among policymakers and business representatives. In fact, it is viewed as one of the factors contributing to the growing importance of VET in the country (see 3.1). However, our review also highlights numerous challenges related to the framework:

- Many occupational standards are created by training providers due to the limited personnel capacity of the VET Centre. This creates the risk that standards are shaped according to the interests of a few influential training providers. Consequently, closely related standards may emerge, potentially undermining the goal of a more transparent and effective system.
- The increasing number of standards makes ongoing updates increasingly unlikely.
- The relationship between individual standards and formal VET programmes, especially the four-year programmes, is unclear in many cases.
- So far, the framework appears to have made little contribution to permeability in the education system. The stages presented within it essentially represent the hierarchical classification of existing VET and adult education programmes. Access to higher education still requires a state matura, both before and after the establishment of the framework.
- Furthermore, the recognition of qualifications from adult education (in the form of National Vocational Qualifications) for acquiring a formal VET qualification has not been possible. Although the revised VET Law suggests this possibility, this addition may be removed in the final version, or may face significant implementation challenges.

In facing these challenges, North Macedonia is not alone. Research on the implementation of National Qualifications Frameworks suggests that their goals are often not achieved in many countries worldwide (Allais, 2017; Young & Allais, 2013). An important insight is that permeability in the education system does not automatically result from the creation of a Qualifications Framework. It is typically a consequence of dedicated negotiations, primarily between policy makers and educational providers, aimed at improving the transition between programmes located at different educational levels or in different areas of the education system, especially between academic and vocational education.

3.4.4 Strengthening post-secondary education (taken from our other article)

The promotion of non-academic, vocationally-oriented post-secondary education is a policy goal in many European countries, as it would offer more learning opportunities to people without access to higher education. Yet, given the expansion of academic higher education and the growing number of university graduates, such efforts often face major challenges (OECD, 2022; State Statistical Office, 2023a; UNDP, 2020).

Strengthening the post-secondary level has been an important education policy goal in North Macedonia, too, and one that receives considerable European IPA-support. However, unlike the qualifications framework approach and the concept of dual VET, post-secondary VET has existed in North Macedonia for a long time, with degrees regulated under the existing VET law, as well as under the aforementioned law on the Qualifications Framework, in which they were assigned to level 5B (Republic of Macedonia, 2013b). In addition, most VET schools in the country are currently

verified as providers of post-secondary education. Graduates from post-secondary education take a specialist exam or master exam, leading to diploma for specialist or master, which allow entrance on the labour market. Qualifications obtained through post-secondary education, although at NQF level 5B, are not recognised in higher education, and do not allow such vertical mobility.

Some reforms are under discussion: in the new draft VET Act, it is proposed that gymnasium graduates (especially those who have completed the four-year VET programme) be admitted more easily to post-secondary education, by no longer requiring them to have three years of work experience prior to enrolment. Additionally, numerous actions focusing on post-secondary VET are being carried out within the framework of the above-mentioned EU project to promote the attractiveness of VET, including initiating a feasibility study of the capacities of providers of post-secondary education, creating a roadmap for implementing post-secondary education, designing concrete post-secondary programmes, and finally launching a campaign to promote them.

Despite the existing regulatory framework and all current efforts, the number of post-secondary education graduates remains insignificant. Most programmes have virtually no students – one of the only exceptions being the one for "driving instructors" (i.e., 184 out of 258 students at this level in 2017/2018) (Ministry of Education and Science, 2023a; State Statistical Office, 2023a). The higher demand for this particular qualification is owed to the simple fact that the authorities actually only admit driving instructors who have this specific degree. Otherwise, however, post-secondary education qualifications lack value in the labour market. In many sectors in which they used to be a prerequisite at the intermediate qualification level in the Yugoslavian planned economy, e.g., in manufacturing or in some of the craft occupations, they no longer play a role. Jobs at this qualification level are instead filled by people with long-standing work experience – or by university graduates with some relevant on-the-job training.

3.4.5 Vocational counselling services

Vocational counselling services have a lengthy history, originating from the ex-Yugoslav educational system, where schools typically offered professional orientation services, often provided by school psychologists. However, over recent decades, these services haven't seen further development, mainly due to the limited significance of 2 and 3-year VET programmes, which would prepare individuals for direct entry into the labour market. More recently, however, counselling services have garnered increasing political attention.

The 2019 Law on Primary Education, for instance, now mandates professional orientation services for students, with schools assisting parents, guardians, and students in selecting a secondary school based on individual characteristics, abilities, and interests. To facilitate this, school psychologists or pedagogues employ tools to identify students' abilities and interests, implementing a professional orientation program for them during the eighth and ninth grades.

At the secondary level, in collaboration with international donors, the MOES established and equipped 52 career centres in public secondary schools across various municipalities. Trained career counsellors, including teachers and professional staff (psychologists/pedagogues) from schools, run career counselling programmes for high school students in these centres. To support this, 180 teachers and professional staff (psychologists/pedagogues) underwent training. This included 117 career counsellors from 52 public vocational schools with established career centres and 63 teachers from 24 vocational schools lacking such centres.

The new draft Law on Secondary Education, for the first time, mandates the nationwide establishment of career counselling services, defining the position of a career counsellor as a distinct category of professionals. Schools will form career counselling teams coordinated by a career counsellor, collaborating with professional staff and teachers. These teams will implement career counselling programmes for students within the school.

These developments are certainly welcome. However, the efforts in recent years, as well as the planned legislative changes, highlight that the focus of career counselling services could aim at

optimal preparation for tertiary-level studies. The transition to the job market after VET at the secondary level is hardly a central focus – and this is undoubtedly not in the interest of companies that engage, for instance, in dual VET. At the same time, within the framework of career counselling, the opportunities offered by dual VET can only be highlighted if it genuinely provides added value in terms of a rewarding job.

3.4.6 Establishing a system of validation of prior learning

The establishment of a system of validation of prior learning has been a long-standing concern in the education policy of North Macedonia. This goal was first articulated in the VET strategy of 2013 (Ministry of Education and Science, 2013b). More concrete steps were outlined in the "Roadmap for implementing a system for validation of non-formal and informal learning" (Ministry of Education and Science & Adult Education Centre, 2016). It suggested that validation "in the short and medium term should focus on arrangements for the awarding of full or partial qualifications" (p. 35) (e.g., in VET at upper secondary level), and that in the longer term, higher education qualifications should also be considered. Aligned with these plans, the country's latest education strategy then proposed that validation should "allow for [...] horizontal and vertical mobility within the education system and the labour market" (Ministry of Education and Science, 2018).

Yet, this assertion has yet to be realised: Access to formal VET qualifications (or their components) hasn't been feasible through the validation process. Substantial changes, however, have been proposed through draft laws that remain pending adoption. The new draft law on NQF generally proposes the potential acquisition of qualifications via prior learning validation, outlining the establishment of a system for validating non-formal and informal learning. Furthermore, the new draft Law on Adult Education defines the validation process, its scope, provider responsibilities, candidate eligibility, and introduces the concept of VNFIL, applicable in both formal and non-formal education. It also presents an opportunity for young and adult individuals not engaged in employment, education, or training (NEETs) to enrol in 'second chance' education and training programmes, thereby broadening flexible VET pathways.

In addition, and complementary to these legal reforms, several important actions were undertaken in the areas of this thematic priority.

- During 2020 and 2021, AEC developed standards for occupations and qualifications "Counsellor for VNFIL" and "Assessor in VNFIL", and further the process of validation was successfully piloted on a small number of candidates.
- In November 2022, the MOES adopted the 'Concept document on secondary education for adults' (MOES, 2022), which proposes the VNFIL as one of the main pillars of adults' secondary education, offering concrete arrangements both in formal and non-formal education.
- As part of the IPA project "Increasing Attractiveness, Inclusiveness and Relevance of VET and Adult Education", the MOES and the VET Centre with an expert support by the project office selected five qualifications (Hairdresser/hairstylist, Auto body repair technician, Baker, Bee breeder, and Dressmaker) and defined the relative standards. These qualifications will be offered and "tested" for validation after the adoption of the new Law on AE.

While these developments are generally welcomed by many stakeholders, the strong theoretical orientation of formal VET poses a significant challenge for validation. The target group of this approach brings important vocational experiences and skills, but these clearly hold less significance in formal VET (including in final examinations). A meaningful approach could involve exempting individuals whose vocational competencies have been validated from the practical components of the education and supporting them in catching up on the theoretical aspects of the training.

3.5 Assessing opportunities and challenges in formal VET

3.5.1 Opportunities

- **High awareness:** Many stakeholders in North Macedonia are aware that the continuous expansion of the higher education sector isn't particularly socially, economically, or financially sensible. This is especially true considering that many individuals with a higher education degree either struggle to find employment or leave the country.
- **Support for the key role of VET:** Numerous key stakeholders believe that formal vocational education and training (VET) should carry even more weight and are motivated to support reforms that can make VET more relevant for the job market.
- **Support from large companies:** Particularly, some larger companies are interested in graduates from VET schools and are already engaging in their training.
- **Funding from international partners:** Due to the significant relevance of VET for the Macedonian context and the current international attention VET is receiving, international donors are willing to support the further development of VET in the coming years.

3.5.2 Challenges

- **Limited importance of vocational qualifications in the labour market:** This is the biggest challenge for the development of vocational education in North Macedonia. Vocational qualifications, especially those at the secondary level, hold little relevance in the job market. Many industries targeted by vocational education (such as gastronomy, construction, craftsmanship, and manufacturing) do not require such qualifications. Usually, completing primary education is sufficient, especially given the significant shortage of labour. The described larger industrial companies interested in VET graduates are in the minority. Positions at higher qualification levels (in the service sector as well as in industry) are typically awarded to individuals with higher education degrees. Consequently, there is currently little incentive for young people to pursue vocational qualifications.
- **Academic orientation of VET:** Despite criticisms about the academic focus of VET at the secondary level, the key stakeholders are ultimately unwilling to fundamentally question this orientation. It is crucial because VET graduates are specifically prepared for higher education. If the theoretical content of secondary VET were significantly reduced, this permeability would be questioned, potentially reducing the societal demand for vocational education. Paradoxically, the current limitation of places in gymnasiums (high schools) can only be justified in the public eye as long as vocational education continues to provide access to higher education – especially considering that vocational qualifications hold little significance in much of the job market.
- **Few expanding VET sectors:** Although the number of VET students is increasing, this growth is limited to a few programmes (medicine, law, economics, engineering), primarily those perceived as promising pathways for pursuing higher education.
- **Challenges for dual VET:** The limited significance of vocational qualifications and the academic orientation of vocational education pose significant challenges, particularly for dual VET. The lack of importance diminishes students' incentive to acquire practical skills, especially when these skills play a minor role in final assessments. As many students aim for higher education after completing VET, substantial efforts will be necessary to ensure sustained engagement by companies in dual VET programmes. These challenges are particularly pronounced concerning small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) where employment conditions are often relatively less attractive.

4 Non-formal Vocational Education and Training

Non-formal VET in North Macedonia, according to our analysis, comprises three areas that are challenging to clearly delineate from each other:

- *Recognised forms of Adult Education*: These are educational offerings regulated by the Law on Adult Education enacted in 2009 (with subsequent amendments until 2018) (Republic of Macedonia, 2009), falling under the purview of the MOES and the Adult Education Centre (AEC). This law opens up the possibility of verifying non-formal education programmes, allowing course participants to access nationally recognised non-formal educational qualifications not acknowledged within the formal education system. Many of these offerings are self-financed by the participants themselves.
- *Active labour market measures*: These measures are financed by the Ministry of Labour and Social Policy and encompass verified course programmes, but also a shorter training programmes that do not lead to a nationally recognised non-formal educational qualification, such as supported employment.
- *Unrecognised, commercial forms of non-formal VET*: In North Macedonia, any legal entity is permitted to establish a commercial training centre and offer non-formal courses without the necessity of verification. This offering is extensive and, although specific figures are unavailable, is heavily utilised, especially in urban areas of the country. It includes courses in rapidly evolving sectors like IT or language instruction.

4.1 Governance and financing

4.1.1 Verification of adult education providers and programmes

The Law on Adult Education stipulates that providers of training can be both public and private institutions for adult education, provided they meet the specified criteria. According to this law, the AEC, in collaboration with the MOES, plays a central role in overseeing non-formal education.

The MOES holds the responsibility of verifying institutions as providers of non-formal education and training, establishing specific requirements concerning staffing, equipment, didactic materials, and premises conditions, among others. Providers initiate the verification process by submitting an application to the AEC, which initially reviews these applications for formalities and subsequently forwards them to the MOES for official verification. The ministry then convenes a 'verification commission' to evaluate compliance with the defined regulations outlined in the by-law. While a significant portion of these providers consists of commercial training providers, chambers and trade unions as well as public institutions (“Установи”), such as schools and open universities, can also strive to become verified providers.

The providers firstly need their programmes to be verified by the AEC. Verification is valid for a period of three years. Upon successful verification, providers must also undergo a verification of the institution as provider, a task overseen by the MOES. There are two different types of programmes in this regard.

- *Programmes for qualifications*. These programmes are supposed to be developed based on existing occupational standards (example: hairdresser, bricklayer etc). Yet, many of these programmes are lacking an alignment with occupational or qualifications standards, and therefore lack information on defined credits and information on the obtained NQF level. To establish a legal foundation for their courses, providers of programmes aiming for verification often find themselves initially responsible for proposing the development of an occupational standard. This proposed standard is then further refined by the VET Centre.
- *Programmes for skills*: These programmes don't necessarily have practical value for employment in the labour market. Examples are computer or language courses.

The AEC register currently consists of 332 verified programmes (Adult Education Centre, 2023).

As the verification is limited to three years, currently, there are 74 out of a total of 180 recognised providers who do not offer verified programmes (Ministry of Education and Science, 2023b). The advantage of having the programmes verified, is that the candidates have certificates recognised nationally, as well as they can be registered in the Employment Services Agency with a concrete qualification obtained, which could potentially lead to an opportunity for employment. The benefit for the providers of having the programmes verified is that with them they can apply for funds to carry out trainings (see below).

4.1.2 Financing of non-formal education through the Employment Services Agency

The MOES generally refrains from participating in financing non-formal education offerings. Instead, public budget allocations for non-formal VET primarily come under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Labour and Social Policy through the “Operational Plan for Active Measures for Employability and Labour Market Needs” that is designed and implemented by the Employment Service Agency (ESA), relying on its own labour market needs analysis.

These active labour measures encompass, as mentioned above, verified course programmes, as well as shorter training programmes that do not lead to a nationally recognised qualification, such as supported employment. Funds are allocated through a competitive submission process to providers offering verified training programmes aimed at unemployed individuals or for honing skills essential for the labour market.

Programmes designed for specific target groups often rely on additional financial resources, frequently sourced from international partners. One notable instance is the E4E project, funded by SDC, which has thus far provided financial support for training to approximately 4650 beneficiaries. Another significant initiative is the Youth Guarantee network, offering programmes and training for young individuals not involved in education, employment, or training (NEETs). This network includes an apprenticeship programme catering to NEETs, which engaged 1063 young participants in 2022. Additionally, specific training initiatives funded by international organisations through the ESA aim to support particularly vulnerable groups, such as the Roma community.

4.2 Statistics

Due to the diverse landscape of non-formal VET, there is no general statistics available for all of it. Against this backdrop, the following section highlights some particularly relevant insights from various sources.

For instance, the analysis from the 2021 Census in Table 5 shows that a very high number of people in North Macedonia, 248'582, participated in non-formal education in that year, representing a share of 26.3% of the economically active population⁴ in the country. This analysis also indicates that a significant majority of these individuals (95%) were employed.

Table 5: Participation in non-formal education (State Statistical Office, 2022a)

Economic activity	Total	Men	Women
Total	248'582	124'525	124'057
Employed	232'552	117'265	115'287
Unemployed	13'391	7'260	6'131
Unactive population	2'640	-	2'640

The recognised forms of Adult Education, which are courses verified by the AEC (see Table 6), constitute only a small part of the usage of non-formal adult education depicted in Table 5. In 2022, this proportion stood at approximately 99.5%. However, the number of participants in such verified

⁴ In the third quarter of 2021, as per the Employment Service Agency (2022), the economically active population amounted to 945'158 individuals.

courses has increased over the past years. Table 6 also indicates that the utilisation of individual programmes, on average, is very low. For instance, in 2022, there were 136 verified programmes, but only 135 trainings were conducted, attended by a total of 1'231 individuals. This suggests that each accredited programme in 2022 was attended by an average of just over 9 people, portraying this system as comparatively inefficient.

Table 6: Verified programmes, trainings and participants (Ministry of Education and Science, 2023b)

Year	Verified programmes for adults	Trainings realised	Number of participants
2018	87	94	965
2019	134	60	753
2020	66	83	1'062
2021	98	122	1'073
2022	136	135	1'231
Total	521	494	5'084

Table 7 provides information on the Active Labour Market Measures within the framework of the ESA's "Operational Plan." It indicates that apprenticeship programmes were particularly utilised, followed by trainings for advanced IT-skills. Notably, the data on expenditures per person are significant. The costs for the apprenticeship programme are comparatively low, whereas they are notably higher for trainings focusing on vocational qualifications demanded by employers.

Table 7: Active labour market measures in 2022 (Employment Services Agency, 2023)

Programme type	Number of beneficiaries	Out of which young	Out of which women	Budget (in MKD)	Expenditure per person (MKD)
Apprenticeship programmes ⁵	1'520	1319	978	44'700'000	29'408
Training for advanced IT skills	424	323	195	39'719'048	93'677
Vocational trainings based on the demand by employers	139	79	87	11'734'944	84'424
Training for vocational qualifications demanded by employers	15	5	10	11'041'944	736'130
Training at job position for known employer	8	7	3	1'260'000	157'500

The comparison between Table 5 and Tables 6 and 7 makes it clear that a significant portion of non-formal education occurs outside of state intervention and is primarily financed by users or employers. Courses offered on the market comprise a wide variety, mostly in personal services (like cosmetics, hairdressing, pedicure, manicure, massages, and lately makeup artists), languages and computer skills. In the last years, trainings in energy sectors attract significant attention, like installers of solar panels, or installers of energy-efficient materials and facades. According to a survey from 2019, around 40% of programmes are in personal services, 30% in hospitality and tourism, 10% in health and social care, and 20% in all other sectors. 31% of all male attendees were in machine engineering sector.

⁵ Also offered to 36 Roma individuals.

4.3 Validation of prior learning in view of non-formal qualifications

The establishment of a system for the validation of prior learning in North Macedonia has been considered since 2013. However, access to formal VET qualifications through validation is not yet possible (3.4.6). To a certain, albeit very limited extent, validation has developed in the non-formal VET sector. In this regard, the AEC, with support from the ETF, has issued several regulations on validation, such as guidance notes for the validation process and a handbook for assessors (ETF & Adult Education Centre, 2017a, 2017b).

Yet, even in the realm of non-formal education, the implementation of validation is not significantly advanced: In fact, to date, vocational competencies have only been validated in the framework of pilot projects funded by external donors. The most relevant example is that of "Build up Skills", a project supported by the EU through its Horizon 2020 program, which aimed at improving skills in the field of energy-efficient construction. Within the framework of this project, 967 workers from 5 different occupations obtained skills certificates (valid in the frames of the project partners) stating that they were competent in the field of energy-efficient construction. Though validation played an important role in the overall design – and also in the reporting – of this project, participants in fact developed most of the necessary skills through training, rather than through a recognition of previously acquired competencies (Build up Skills, 2016a, 2016b; Spasovski, 2018). More recently, under a donor-funded initiative that piloted validation in the years 2020-2021, and realised by AEC in cooperation with MOES, seven candidates received their waiter certificate, positioned at level 3 of the MQF, that would otherwise be issued after a short training program. Under the same initiative, it had been planned to validate the skills of facade workers, but due to low demand, no qualification was awarded in this occupation (Adult Education Centre, 2021).

In our view, the pilot schemes to validate competencies have generated little demand primarily because the non-formal qualifications made accessible by these initiatives have hardly any added value for employability in the Macedonian labour market. Access to the jobs for which these qualifications are designed is basically possible even without such qualifications – and in those parts of the labour market that could be attractive for the target groups (e.g., better-paid jobs in the services sector in the urban areas of the country), formal qualifications at upper secondary or higher education level are required. The expected establishment and functioning of the departments for validation and AE in the Regional VET Centres should provide crucial redesigning and support to development, rationale and sustainability of the validation arrangements.

4.4 Assessing opportunities and challenges in non-formal VET

4.4.1 Opportunities

- **Increasing economic and social demand:** Given that formal VET and higher education rarely impart directly applicable practical skills for the workplace, there exists a substantial interest in the job market for newly recruited employees to possess these skills nonetheless. Employees also recognise this economic demand, thereby elevating the social demand for non-formal VET.
- **Key economic sectors:** This social demand for non-formal VET is particularly high in sectors that offer comparatively good remuneration, primarily situated in urban areas, and mostly requiring employees to have higher education qualifications. A prime example is the IT industry.
- **Positive perception by trainees:** Trainees engaging in commercial non-formal VET typically perceive these programmes as highly relevant. From their standpoint, non-formal VET represents a viable option for individuals seeking specific skills or career advancement, even in the absence of prior knowledge in the field.

4.4.2 Challenges

- **Limited labour market recognition for the poorest:** Non-formal VET qualifications hold minimal value in many sectors of the labour market, especially those accessible to poorer individuals who do not possess completed secondary or higher education. In numerous sectors (excluding high technology-related fields and regulated professions), individuals could secure employment without a certificate.
- **Ambiguous value addition of verified courses within active labour market measures:** While commercial courses are attended to support participants' career prospects, it remains uncertain whether non-formal education courses funded by the ESA for various target groups genuinely enhance their position in the job market. This added value seems to be particularly low for the poorest. There is substantial evidence indicating that courses targeting unemployed higher education graduates also offer limited improvement in their job market standing.
- **Limited recognition in the education system, both domestically and internationally:** Despite efforts to promote adult education through a separately established unit (Adult Education Centre) and the integration of adult education into the MQF, these efforts contributed minimally to the recognition of adult education within the education system. Graduates of adult education lack access to formal education unless they meet conventional admission requirements. Moreover, while the MQF is referenced to the EQF, non-formal qualifications from North Macedonia hold no significance in education systems, and very low significance in the labour markets of Western European countries.
- **Insufficient institutional capacity:** The political aim to promote non-formal adult education assumed its ability to adapt swiftly to changes in the job market compared to formal VET. Unfortunately, both the AEC and the VET Centre lack the capacity to promptly develop or adapt occupational and qualification standards in response to changes in the labour market.
- **Standards developed without demand orientation:** Due to limited capacity within the AEC and VET Centre, training providers are often tasked with defining occupational and qualification standards, frequently without involvement from representatives of the workforce. This poses the risk that such official standards align more with the commercial interests of specific providers rather than the actual demands of the labour market.
- **Tedious verification process:** The verification procedure is slow, complex (requiring numerous documents and steps), and expensive. Additionally, all verifications, regardless of the sector or labour market dynamics, remain valid for the same period – three years.
- **Lack of quality control:** While non-formal education is praised for its practical approach and real-world problem-solving, it faces criticism for rushing courses, lacking a selection process, and lacking quality assurance mechanisms for assessing competencies.

5 Recommendations

5.1 Overall recommendations

- **Limit access to higher education:** VET can only regain prominence if access to higher education is restricted. While this strategy carries political risks, it would not only benefit VET itself, the economy, and society as a whole, but also enhance the credibility of higher education degrees.
- **Clearly communicate regarding pending legislative drafts:** Currently, three legislative drafts related to VET are pending. Relevant stakeholders are unaware of the intended enactment timeline for these drafts. The government should urgently provide transparent details regarding its plans in this area. Articles that seem logical in theory but are impractical to implement should be reconsidered.
- **Strengthen career counselling services in primary and secondary schools:** Policymakers should allocate additional resources to bolster career counselling services in schools. This could effectively highlight the significance of VET, elucidating its roles and benefits to students while supporting their vocational interests and aptitudes.
- **Boost the evidence-base of VET policy:** Currently, there is limited data available on the post-graduation pursuits of VET graduates. Therefore, the recently initiated "tracer studies" should continue and be placed on a solid financial footing to provide comprehensive insights.

5.2 Recommendations on formal VET in general

- **Fundamentally rethink the role of secondary VET:** Presently, there's strong promotion of enrolment in four-year programmes of secondary VET, emphasizing the pathway to higher education for VET graduates. This hinders reforms seeking to enhance the practical orientation of secondary VET. Promoting VET that directly prepares students for the workforce would require labour market recognition of such qualifications. Restricting access to higher education, as mentioned earlier, could facilitate this shift.
- **Rethink the network of VET schools:** Establishing regional VET centres is an essential initial step. However, the provision of VET schools should be even more centrally coordinated on a national level to prevent competition among municipalities and their respective schools.
- **Improve remedial programmes:** Current remedial programmes mainly concentrate on exam preparation, lacking substantial teaching, practical training, and work-based learning. To maximise benefits for candidates and the labour market, comprehensive improvements are needed. One potential solution involves aligning these programmes with measures for recognizing prior learning, ensuring quality training for candidates following assessment phases.
- **Develop a realistic validation strategy for formal VET:** The goal of making secondary VET qualifications accessible through validation is ambitious, considering their highly theoretical nature. A more realistic approach would involve focusing on select VET programmes in comparatively high demand in the labour market (e.g., energy sector and social care) and allowing access to partial qualifications through validation, focusing on the vocational aspects of these programmes.
- **Cultivate a supportive and inclusive culture in VET schools:** VET schools typically enrol vulnerable and underachieving students, facing unique challenges due to the specific characteristics of the sector. Establishing a supportive and inclusive culture is crucial for creating conducive conditions that foster healthy growth and efficient vocational development among students.

5.3 Recommendations for dual VET in particular

- **Develop a realistic assessment of the added value for businesses and students:** From a political standpoint, the introduction of dual VET is immensely relevant and appealing. However, many conditions necessary for the successful establishment of this model are lacking, particularly the role of vocational secondary education qualifications in the job market. This diminishes significant incentives for both students to acquire practical skills and for businesses to engage in training.
- **Establish a sustainable funding strategy:** Currently, many learners enrol in dual VET due to financial support, and businesses also expect financial compensation for their involvement. The MOES needs to thoroughly examine its capacity for sustainable financing of these initiatives before defining legal provisions.
- **Clarify the aim of company-based training components:** Students participating in dual VET programmes at companies are currently minimally engaged in productive activities, often observing operational processes, frequently in groups. This inadequacy in developing vocational competencies often renders the engagement in training unattractive for businesses. The objective should be to actively involve dual VET students in productive tasks. If that isn't feasible, restricting company-based training to summer practices might be a more favourable alternative, also from the students' perspective.
- **Gradually expand dual VET in branches/companies where it makes most sense:** Industries and firms unable to provide attractive prospects for VET graduates and good training conditions should refrain from adopting the dual model. Therefore, focusing dual VET on a select few major companies and their students in specialised classes at vocational schools might be necessary, while other students receive training outside the dual VET system.
- **Increase the weight of practical competencies in the final exam:** Dual VET is meaningful only if practical competencies hold significant weight in the final exam; otherwise, students have little incentive to acquire them.

5.4 Recommendations on non-formal VET

- **Rethink the verification process:** The current process for verifying providers and programmes is lengthy and too demanding for the providers. MOES and AEC should collaborate to redesign it in partnership with providers to make it more streamlined and efficient.
- **Ensure involvement of labour market representatives in the development of standards:** Currently, many standards are devised by providers themselves. Involving labour market representatives in standard development would ensure alignment with actual market demands.
- **Establish quality assurance mechanisms:** To increase the value of non-formal programmes and training, it's crucial to introduce quality assurance mechanisms that assess the skills acquired. This is particularly important in validation processes, where ensuring and maintaining quality has been a significant concern in recent years.

6 Literature

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7 Annexes

7.1 Objectives of the assignment (as formulated by Helvetas)

Objectives of the assignment

Main Objective:

The main objective of the review of the VSD System in North Macedonia is to assess the current state-of-affairs and identify gaps and areas of improvement within the VSD system, resulting in better and more decent employment opportunities for citizens of North Macedonia, with specific emphasis on young people.

Objectives of the Review:

1. To provide an overview of the current VSD system in North Macedonia, including its structure, key stakeholders, policy developments, and the impact it has had on formal VET and non-formal VET practices.
2. To analyse the gaps present in both formal and non-formal VET– the two main branches of VSD – and offer recommendations for enhancing the system's efficiency effectiveness in meeting the demands of the job market as well as the needs of students and learners.
3. To assess the effectiveness and outcomes of the Dual VET programs within the VSD system in North Macedonia, with a focus on evaluating the level of industry relevance, employer involvement, and student satisfaction.

Additionally, the review aims to assist the key decision makers namely, MoES, ECNM, and MoLSP, in further developing the VSD system.

7.2 Overview of interviews

Organisation	Name	Position	Date
VET Centre Skopje	Sherif Miftari	Director of the VET Centre	02.10.2023
	Ardijana Paloshi	Adviser	02.10.2023
	Elizabeta Jovanovska Radanovic	Adviser	02.10.2023
	Ridvan Zequri	Adviser	02.10.2023
	Azra Tutic	Adviser	02.10.2023
RVETC Kumanovo	Vesna Trajkovska	Director	03.10.2023
RVETC Kumanovo	Focus group	VET Teachers	03.10.2023
RVETC Kumanovo	Focus group	Students in dual education	03.10.2023
Non-formal provider "Vizija" - Kumanovo	Vidan Dodevski	Owner and instructor	03.10.2023
Economic Chamber	Natasha Janevska	Project manager	02.10.2023
Organisation of Employers of Macedonia	Svetlana Ristovska Antic	President	04.10.2023
Non-formal provider- Open Workers University KocoRacin	Mane Kolev	Instructor and ex-director	04.10.2023
Non-formal provider SOLAR	Stefan Trajkov	Owner and instructor	04.10.2023
Non-formal provider SEMOS Education	Angjelina Kanchevska	Instructor	04.10.2023
VET school SUGS "Dimitar Vlahov" - Skopje	Biljana	VET teacher	27.09.2023
Regional center RVETCs "Moshka Pijade" - Tetovo	Faton Mustafi	VET teacher	28.09.2023
VET school SOU "Gjorche Petrov" – Kriva Palanka	Dragana	VET teacher	28.09.2023
VET school SOU "Nikola Karev" - Strumica	Milica	VET teacher	30.09.2023
VET school SOU "Aco Rusinski" - Berovo	Angel & Fimka	VET teachers	03.10.2023
VET school SOTU "Gjorgji Naumov" - Bitola	Hristina	VET teacher	11.10.2023
VET school SOU "Bogdanci" – Bogdanci	Slobodancho –	VET teacher	09.10.2023
VET school- SUGS "Dimitar Vlahov" - Skopje	Focus group with students in dual education	Students	09.10.2023
VET school– OSU "Aco Ruskovski" - Berovo	Focus group with Students in dual education	Students	25.10.2023
VET school– SOU "Gjorche Petrov" - Kriva Palanka	Focus group with Students in dual education	Students	25.10.2023
Non-formal VET – student at Kocho Racin	Maja	Student	20.10.2023
Non-formal VET – student at Kocho Racin	Elena	Student	24.10.2023
Non-formal VET – student at SEMOS Education	Proshe	Student	26.10.2023
Non-formal VET – student at SEMOS Education	Sofija	Student	26.10.2023
Organisations providing DE "TREND-DE-SIGN LLC Delchevo"Export - Import	Zhaklina	Mentor	18.10.2023
Organisations providing DE- JP National Forests, "Branch Bigla Demir Hisar"	Ilcho	Mentor	18.10.2023
Organisations providing DE- "Private Health Institution Dr. Angela Murdzheva"	Angela	Mentor	26.10.2023
Organisations providing DE- "Notary Tanja Asporova"	Tanja	Mentor	26.10.2023
Organisations providing DE- Company for production, trade, and services "NON-FI Delchevo"	Lenche	Mentor	30.10.2023
Organisations providing DE- Company for Audit Bend Audit and Consulting "LLC Tetovo"	Bojana	Mentor	30.10.2023
Organisations providing DE- Company for Audit Bend Audit and Consulting "LLC Tetovo"	Naim	Mentor	30.10.2023

Organisations providing DE- "Chateau Sopot DOO"	Sashko	Mentor	30.10.2023
Organisations providing DE - "DTU EXTRA BOHEM DOOEL"	Trjache	Mentor	30.10.2023
Organisations providing DE - "Pharmacies Eurofarm - Bitola"	Daniela	Mentor	30.10.2023